

Thermal Decomposition of Diaquo bis (γ -picoline N-oxide) Nickel(II) Chloride and its Reaction with 4-vinyl, -methyl and -cyanopyridines

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A yellow, paramagnetic tetrahedral Nickel(II) complex, $[\text{NiL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, where L is γ -picoline N-oxide was isolated and characterised. Thermal decomposition studies of this compound revealed that at 145° , a purple coloured diamagnetic solid, $[\text{NiL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$, and at 220° a green coloured paramagnetic complex having the composition $[\text{Ni}_2\text{L}_2\text{Cl}_4]$ were obtained. The coordinated water molecules are replaced by 4-vinyl, -methyl and -cyano pyridines (L') forming mixed ligand tetrahedral complexes having the composition $[\text{NiL}_2\text{L}'_2]\text{Cl}_2$.

PYRIDINE N-oxide and its derivatives are known to form¹⁻⁷ a large number of complexes with several transitional metal halides and pseudo halides. The majority of complexes prepared from solution contain two ligand molecules for each metal atom with coordinated anions and often lattice solvent or water. However, the most interesting behaviour of these N-oxide ligands is the nature of coordination around the central metal ion. Often, these act as unidentate⁸ ligands. Sometimes they act as bridging⁹ ligands, as in the case of Co(II), Zn(II) and Ni(II) complexes³, with a low ratio of ligand to metal. On account of the possibility of different behaviour of these ligands, we studied the reaction of hydrated NiCl_2 with γ -picoline N-oxide in the present investigation. Further, the thermal decomposition of the isolated complex and its reaction with some substituted pyridines are also studied.

Experimental

1. Diaquo bis(γ -picoline N-oxide) Nickel(II) chloride, $[\text{NiL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$:

Ethanolic solution of A.R. grade $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was refluxed with an ethanolic solution of γ -picoline N-oxide in 1 : 4 molar ratio for one hour. A yellow solid separated out. This was suction filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and finally dried in *vacuo*. It is highly soluble in water but insoluble in common organic solvents.

2. Dichloro bis(γ -picoline N-oxide) Nickel(II), $[\text{NiL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$:

The yellow $[\text{NiL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ on keeping at 145° for one hour is converted to a purple coloured compound having the composition NiL_2Cl_2 . This is soluble in

nitrobenzene. When put in water, it changes colour to yellow and dissolves.

3. $\text{Ni}_2\text{L}_2\text{Cl}_4$:

The purple NiL_2Cl_2 when heated to 220° constant temperature for one hour, changes to green coloured compound answering to the composition $\text{Ni}_2\text{L}_2\text{Cl}_4$. This is soluble in nitrobenzene and also in water with a change of colour as above.

4. Bis(γ -picoline N-oxide) bis (4-vinyl pyridine) Nickel(II) Chloride, $[\text{NiL}_2(4\text{-vpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$:

Ethanolic suspension of $[\text{NiL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ was refluxed for two hours with an ethanol solution of 4-vinyl pyridine in 1 : 2 molar ratio. Gradually the suspension dissolved and a light green solid separated out. It was filtered under suction, washed with ethanol, ether and finally dried in *vacuo*. It is soluble in water, but insoluble in common organic solvents.

5. Bis(4-cyano pyridine) bis(γ -picoline N-oxide) Nickel(II) chloride, $[\text{NiL}_2(4\text{-CNpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$:

The preparation and properties are similar to the above compound. The light green solid had the composition $[\text{NiL}_2(4\text{-CNpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$.

6. Bis(4-methylpyridine) bis(γ -picoline N-oxide) Nickel(II) chloride, $[\text{NiL}_2(4\text{-mepy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$:

A light blue solid was obtained following the same procedure. It is soluble in water but insoluble in common organic solvents.

The above interconversion can be schematically represented as follows :

The percentage loss in weight at 145° is calc.—9.3, found—9.1 and that at 220° is calc.—15.6, found—15.6.

Analysis :

Nickel and chloride were estimated gravimetrically by standard methods as nickel-dimethyl glyoxime and as silver chloride.

Physical measurements :

Infrared spectra in the range $5000\text{--}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded on Nujol mulls using Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on solid specimens using Guoy method. The molar conductance data were measured for $\sim 10^{-3}M$ solution in water and nitrobenzene using Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CL 0102 and dip type cell.

The analytical, conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are recorded in Table 1 and the frequencies of the fundamental vibrations of γ -picoline N-oxide in the complexes are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—STRETCHING FREQUENCIES OF FUNDAMENTAL VIBRATIONS (CM^{-1}) OF γ -PICOLINE N-OXIDE IN Ni(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	$\nu(\text{N-O})$	$\delta(\text{N-O})$	$\gamma(\text{C-H})$
$[\text{NiL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	1205(vs)	845(vs)	750(vs)
NiL_2Cl_2	1205(vs)	850(vs)	760(vs)
$\text{Ni}_2\text{L}_3\text{Cl}_4$	1200(m)	850(br)	755(m)
$[\text{NiL}_2(4\text{-vpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	1222(vs)	830(vs)	715(m)
$[\text{NiL}_2(4\text{-CNpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	1215(br)	840(m)	715(br)
$[\text{NiL}_2(4\text{-mepy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	1220(vs)	865(vs)	715(vs)

vs = very sharp, br = broad, m = medium.

results. The yellow diaquo bis(γ -picoline N-oxide) Nickel(II) chloride loses two molecules of water

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE OF Ni(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Ni (%)		Cl (%)		m.p. $^\circ\text{C}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M mhos
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.			
$[\text{NiL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	15.5	15.4	18.4	18.4	267(d)	3.95	369
NiL_2Cl_2	16.5	16.8	20.2	20.3	—	diamagnetic	0.95
$\text{Ni}_2\text{L}_3\text{Cl}_4$	20.5	20.3	23.9	24.1	—	3.35	0.65
$[\text{NiL}_2(4\text{-vpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	10.2	10.5	12.7	12.7	>250	4.10	380
$[\text{NiL}_2(4\text{-CNpy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	10.4	10.5	12.9	12.7	>250	3.95	389
$[\text{NiL}_2(4\text{-mepy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	11.3	11.0	12.9	13.2	>250	3.92	401

Results and Discussion

The thermal decomposition³ for the pyridine complexes of halides of Mn(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) follows the below given pattern :

at 145° and changes to purple NiL_2Cl_2 . On further heating, this loses at 220° one mole of γ -picoline N-oxide per two moles of NiL_2Cl_2 and is converted to green $\text{Ni}_2\text{L}_3\text{Cl}_4$. Both the purple and green compounds are stable in dry atmosphere but change over to yellow diaquo complex in contact with water.

They can be represented as follows :

Further the diaquo complex $[\text{NiL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ on treatment with 4-vinyl-, cyano and -methyl pyridines (L') gives rise to $[\text{NiL}_2\text{L}'_2]\text{Cl}_2$ where two moles of coordinated water molecules are replaced by two moles of substituted pyridine.

The Λ_M values of the compounds in water are ~ 400 mhos (Table 1) indicating them to be 1:2 electrolytes. The low values for NiL_2Cl_2 and $\text{Ni}_2\text{L}_3\text{Cl}_4$ (≈ 1 mhos) indicate their non-electrolytic nature.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements classify them into three categories: (1) The diamagnetic square planar compound NiL_2Cl_2 involving dsp^2 hybrid orbitals for bonding. (2) Paramagnetic tetrahedral compounds having the general formula $[\text{NiL}_2\text{L}'_2]\text{Cl}_2$. These compounds have μ_{eff} values ranging between 3.5 and 4.1 B.M. (Table 1) indicating the presence of two unpaired electrons with a large orbital contribution as expected for tetrahedral Nickel(II) complexes involving the use of $4s4p^3$ hybrid orbitals. (3) $\text{Ni}_2\text{L}_3\text{Cl}_4$ shows a slightly smaller value of μ_{eff} than the above viz., 3.35 B.M. This may be due to either antiferromagnetic interaction present in the compound or due to the bridging of the ligand or halogen. This aspect will be studied in greater detail later on.

The infrared spectrum of diaquo bis(γ -picoline N-oxide) Nickel(II) chloride shows a broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} and sharp bands at 1630 and 875 cm^{-1} , indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules. These bands are, however, absent in all the other compounds showing that the water molecules are removed on heating or replaced by substituted pyridine. Coordination of γ -picoline N-oxide through the oxygen to central metal ion can be indicated by three fundamental vibrations, viz., $\nu(\text{N}-\text{O})$, $\delta(\text{N}-\text{O})$ and $\gamma(\text{C}-\text{H})$. It has been reported¹¹⁻¹³ that, on complexation the $\nu(\text{N}-\text{O})$ undergoes considerable negative shift, $\delta(\text{N}-\text{O})$ no significant change and $\gamma(\text{C}-\text{H})$ will have either small positive or negative shift or will be at the same position. In the free ligand, these occur at 1252 , 855 and 740 cm^{-1} respectively. The $(\text{N}-\text{O})$ stretching frequency in all the complexes reported, occur in the range 1205 – 1220 cm^{-1} (Table 2). This decrease in frequency from 1252 cm^{-1} in the free ligand is attributed to a change

in the nitrogen-oxygen bond order as a result of oxygen-metal coordination^{13,14}. The $(\text{N}-\text{O})$ bending vibration shows a negative shift in all the complexes, except in the $[\text{NiL}_2(4\text{-mepy})_2]\text{Cl}_2$. This negative shift suggests that the mass effect due to coordinated metal ion on $\delta(\text{N}-\text{O})$, is outweighing the effect due to coordination¹⁵. The $\gamma(\text{C}-\text{H})$ vibration of the ligand has also undergone positive or negative shifts as expected.

Sharp bands at 1630 , 1625 and 1620 cm^{-1} in the i.r. spectra of mixed N-oxide and substituted pyridine complexes definitely suggest the coordination of 4-vinyl-, cyano and -methyl pyridines respectively to central metal ion. These correspond to the absorption bands at 1600 , 1610 and 1594 cm^{-1} of the free unbonded 4-vinyl-, cyano and -methyl pyridines. The thickening of the three fundamental ligand absorption bands in case of $\text{Ni}_2\text{L}_3\text{Cl}_4$ presumably suggest the presence of low-spin isomer in small quantity. The comparatively low magnetic moment of this compound is also in accordance with this observation.

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References

1. R. C. GRAVEY, J. H. NELSON and R. C. RAGSDALE, *Co-ord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, 3, 375.
2. N. M. KARAYANNIS, J. W. MINKILWICZ, L. L. PYTELEWSKI and M. M. LABES, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 1969, 3, 129.
3. D. H. BROWN, D. KENYON and D. W. A. SRAFF, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 1474.
4. D. W. HERLOCKER, R. S. DRAGO and V. I. MEEK, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 2009.
5. I. S. ARUJA and S. RASTOGI, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 1863.
6. T. W. BRILL and W. D. WERTZ, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 2892.
7. A. J. PAPPAS, J. F. VILLA and H. W. POWELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 550.
8. R. S. SAGAR and W. H. WATSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 1358.
9. R. S. SAGAR, R. J. WILLIAMS and W. H. WATSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, 6, 951.
10. R. N. PATEL and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1967, 351, 2.
11. N. M. KARAYANNIS, J. T. CRONIN, C. M. MIKULSKI, L. L. PYTELEWSKI and M. M. LABES, *J. Inorg. and Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 4344.
12. I. S. ARUJA and R. SINGH, *J. Inorg. and Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, 35, 561.
13. R. D. KROSS, V. A. FASSELY and M. MAGOSHES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 1332.
14. J. V. QUAGLIANO, J. FUJITA, G. FRANZ, D. J. PHILLIPS, J. A. WALMSLEY and S. Y. TYREE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 3770.
15. S. KIDA, J. V. QUAGLIANO, J. A. WALMSLEY and S. Y. TYREE, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1963, 19, 189.